

Ficus salicifolia Wonderboom fig

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Group: Eudicot

Size: A small to medium tree up to 12 m high. It can develop a massive canopy through branches rooting and forming “daughter” trunks.

Distribution:

This tree is found from South Africa and Botswana to the Arabian Peninsula, Socotra Island and Egypt. Outlying populations are present in mountains in the Sahara desert.

Importance:

Most *Ficus* species have 26 chromosomes, but tetraploidy has possibly evolved four times within the genus, producing four tetraploid *Ficus* species, all of which occur in South Africa. Although tetraploidy may provide an advantage in South Africa's more seasonal climate, its benefits remain unclear. The assembled genome will help test hypotheses on the evolution and potential adaptive significance of tetraploidy.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 70.76 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 7.9 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 0.81 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 98.6% [Single: 20.9%, Duplicated: 77.6%]
BUSCO database: viridiplantae
Assembly N50: 2 031.03 kilobases
Contig number: 1 242

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